
Research

Strategies to Increase Malian Awareness of the Belt and Road Initiative

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Abstract: Building "the Belt and Road" has helped the countries along it develop economically and in terms of trade and investment. It has also strengthened relations between China and the countries along it in terms of politics, economy, culture, and other areas. As a result, countries along the route have generally supported the "Belt and Road Initiative" since it was launched. Mali, a significant West African nation, and the Chinese government signed a memorandum of understanding on "the Belt and Road" cooperation in 2019, bolstering bilateral ties in a variety of sectors, including infrastructure development, agriculture, energy, education, and healthcare.

Following the start of the "Belt and Road" project in Mali, the awareness of this project among Malian citizens has significantly impacted China and Mali's cooperation. Based on this, the paper discusses the current state of Malian citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction in an effort to thoroughly understand their perceptions of and attitudes toward the project from the standpoint of global communication. The paper makes recommendations for improving Malian Awareness concerning "the Belt and Road" initiative construction's to promote global communication.

Keywords: Belt and Road Initiative, Malian Awareness, Strategies

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Introduction

A new paradigm for global development has emerged with the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which Chinese President Xi Jinping announced in September 2013. More than 150 nations signed cooperation agreements with China in the six years since its launch in 2013, which explains its significance. In contrast to Asia and Europe, where there are many studies on the effects of BRI, Africa has few which is even lesser as far as Mali is concerned. It is increasingly important to evaluate the citizens' levels of cognition and potential motivators with regard to the "Belt and Road" construction as more nations join this initiative. In this paper, the factors influencing Malians' comprehension of the BRI are identified along with their levels of awareness. It also suggests ways to improve Malians' understanding of the "Belt and Road" construction, encouraging their active involvement and contribution.

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) encompasses different aspects and facets which have been critiqued, analyzed and opined on by researchers on a global scale. While some scholars (Tiberghien, 2017; Dossou, 2018; Ubi, 2019) have

assessed BRI as a growth model for Africa, others (Sun, 2015; Dodson, 2017; Deloitte, 2019; as mentioned in Kanai & Schindler, 2019a) have focused on the phenomenon via the lenses of Chinese investment in railway transport infrastructure development in Africa. Keen attention has also been paid to Kenya's Standard Gauge Railway project to establish a route between Mombasa and Nairobi (Irandu, 2018; Kanai & Schindler, 2019a; Irandu & Owilla, 2020). Valuable light has also been shed by Barillé (2020) and Clark (2020) concerning the redefinition of international relations and development within the BRI context in Pakistan as well as Greece and Sri Lanka respectively.

The essence of this paper is further enhanced by the sheer lack of relevant literature regarding BRI in Mali. With the exclusion of international publications (National Development and Reform Commission of the People's Republic of China, 2015; World Bank, 2019; International Media Support, 2019), little to no Mali-specific comprehensive or constructive BRI literature can be found. This also makes the situation surrounding low Malian awareness about BRI unfortunately inevitable. Given the global scale of this initiative, it is crucial that Malians become aware and acquainted with the inner workings, to create ways in which the Sino-Africa as well as China-Mali relations will be improved upon for mutual benefits. This paper will not only be a valuable addition to the existing body of BRI literature, but it will also be a shining light for the role, status and situation of Mali within the BRI. It is also hoped that the information brought forward by this paper will gain the attention of policymakers in Mali as well as to ignite the interest of Malian researchers to pay closer attention to what is a global game-changer.

Here, we will firstly review pertinent literature regarding the Belt and Road Initiative and what it means for the member states involved, with closer attention to Africa and ultimately Mali. We will then assess the primary factor which influences Malians' comprehension of the BRI and their awareness levels. Lastly, we will identify ways to improve the awareness of Malians concerning BRI.

1. Belt and Road Initiative:

1.1 An Overview

Implementing revised "Opening Up" policies is a key component of President Xi Jinping's contemporary plans for Chinese reform in order to boost the country's influence internationally and economic growth. China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), formerly known as the "One Belt, One Road" (OBOR) Initiative, was first introduced by President Xi Jinping in 2013 as a massive infrastructure project aimed at enhancing transport connectivity between nations. With a preliminary focus on Central Asia, the initiative aims to improve regional connectivity and cooperation between countries. The BRI is a reflection of China's efforts to forge a stronger presence in global trade and relations as well as through exchanges that advance Chinese culture. The BRI aims to promote China as the principal representative of Asia by reshaping China's global profile as a result of engaging in international relations and cooperation. The plan lays the foundation for social and economic development, with goals that include enhancing economic prosperity, advancing sustainable development, fostering international cooperation and understanding, and advancing global peace and development (Blanchard, 2017; Xi, 2017a). Therefore, improving trade connectivity through the development of infrastructure and transportation is one of China's national objectives. Through the establishment of corridors in more than 60 nations throughout Eurasia, South Asia, and Africa, the BRI primarily focuses on land transportation using railroads and highways. This network is growing as more nations show interest in joining the BRI to take advantage of improved trade access, infrastructure investments, and related investments from BRI projects like the construction of manufacturing facilities. Additionally, one of the BRI's main initiatives is the 21st Century Maritime Silk Road Initiative (MSRI), which aims to create new and expanded sea trade routes that connect Southeast China with Europe.

In addition to the land routes of the BRI, the Maritime Silk Road Initiative aims to improve sea trade from Southeast Asia through Africa and Europe, and to help the participating countries with economic and infrastructural development projects. The MSRI plays a key role in the development and improvement of maritime trade through its regional connectivity that revolves around the five areas of cooperation. The BRI's "Belt," which focuses on infrastructure

development, is different from the MSRI, which supports China's commercial aspirations through regional cooperation, free trade, and financial integration (Bonciu, 2019; Klemensits, 2018). The MSRI primarily benefits China because it links Southeast Asia to South Asian and European ports, enabling China to use foreign ports to expand its naval presence and create practical trade routes for Chinese goods to travel around the world. This is true despite an emphasis on cooperation between the nations involved in maritime trade (Blanchard, 2017). The MSRI advances China's resource security offers less onerous trade policies, and strengthens the defense of China's commercial interests, giving it access to markets and resources that China requires for its economic growth.

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which emphasizes development through economic and social reforms, puts a challenge to the conventional neoliberal development processes. China's own development strategy has relied on a selective approach to neoliberal policies, such as international investment and providing special economic zones for open market economies, while still upholding their political and economic sovereignty over their unique development goals and organizational structure. The BRI, a significant Chinese government initiative for international development, aims to finance the improvement of infrastructure, increased trade accessibility, and support for the development of participating nations. By participating in the global economy in a selective manner through this initiative, China is applying its economic and societal norms in an effort to expand on its historically low labor costs (Rodrik, 2012). Large-scale capital investment, quick productivity growth, decentralized economic production, and efforts to reduce poverty have all contributed to China's development and evolution toward the status of an advanced economy (Koboević et al., 2018). Although this strategy for development is linked to unfavorable outcomes like information censorship, a rise in income inequality, and a disregard for environmental protection, China was still able to promote rapid economic growth and acquire significant financial and political sway in international affairs using this strategy.

The BRI aims to provide new alternatives for participating nations based on the Chinese development model. This model prioritizes infrastructure development and economic growth without enacting rigid reforms or conditions (Bonciu, 2019). This development model, however, also appears to be a new strategy for China to become a regional and global superpower by putting its own needs first in order to obtain unrestricted trade access everywhere. The BRI case study approach is useful for analyzing its true impact in each country, including how China has invested in projects and what has been accomplished, in order to ascertain the initiative's short- and long-term effects on a national and international scale. Through the BRI, China is present and investing in other nations, challenging current international relations by avoiding political conflict and emphasizing economic growth and development. Although China has long been a significant player in the world order, its economy and political clout have only recently increased to such a degree (Greer, 2018).

1.2 An Insight into the BRI in Africa

China has a long history of involvement in Africa (N'Diaye, 2016). These bilateral contacts have always been started by China, and this is still the case today. Chinese-African cooperation has significantly increased, and it has recently become the focus of in-depth research (Alden, Alao, Zhang, Barber, 2018; Brautigam, 2015; Chen, 2016; Cheng, Taylor, 2017; Conteh-Morgan, 2017; Lin, Wang, 2017; Stahl, 2017; Wekesa, 2016; ZiroMwatela, Changfeng, 2016; as mentioned in Kaczmarek, 2019). Some of these studies focus on The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), whose significance is closely linked to China's prominence in the global economy and politics as well as the anticipated role China will play in geopolitics (Koodko, 2018). The involvement of some African states in the BRI, which has the potential to easily and quickly expand to include more nations in Africa, may only hint at the extent of China's presence in the continent. But even if it doesn't, China is highly unlikely to scale back its current close cooperation with partners in Africa that aren't formally a part of the BRI (Angola, Nigeria, Democratic Republic of Congo, Congo, Guinea, Equatorial Guinea). However, the growth of the BRI could have a significant impact on China's policy toward Africa, both strategically and practically, by ensuring the coherence of Chinese policies for Africa, for example. China also makes use of the ambiguity of its Initiative, claiming that it is consistent with the national development plans of various African nations, such as

Kenya's Vision 2030 and President Uhuru Kenyatta's "Big Four" Agenda (Xianfa, 2018, as mentioned in Kaczmarek, 2019). This continues China's previous promises to Africa, which were succinctly stated by Hu Jintao, Chairman of the People's Republic of China, who stated that China sincerely supports the freedom of African countries to choose their own development path while assisting them in maximizing their own development potential (after: N'Diaye, 2016: 216). The BRI, however, was not preceded by consultations with potential partners; rather, it was an idea that originated in China. The idea that "economic growth without political liberalization or accountability is not only possible, but advantageous" is actually promoted by this (Koodko, 2018).

Two of the three African countries that are a part of the BRI, Egypt and Djibouti, are ideally situated in the center of the world's geopolitical arena. Since it now houses military bases for the US, France, and China, Djibouti is quite exceptional. The war against pirates has frequently been cited as the driving force behind this, but it's hard to argue that power struggles are the real reason these great powers have such a strong military presence in the area. China's entry into the region and Djibouti could cause security alliances that have supported international order since 1945 to shift and realign (The Sun, 2016; as mentioned in ZiroMwatela & Changfeng, 2016). Egypt is the only country in Africa to formally sign bilateral agreements on the Belt and Road initiative with China because of its strategically important location at the Suez Canal. Egypt simply cannot be left out of the initiative. However, rather than being the result of official declarations, the inclusion of Djibouti has been the result of "logical" assumptions. As previously mentioned, this can be solely explained in terms of the horn of Africa's geopolitics and the desire for world dominance. Djibouti and Egypt are crucial because 30% of the world's shipping passes through the Red Sea's entrance from the Indian Ocean to the Suez Canal (Financial Times, April 1, 2016; as per ZiroMwatela & Changfeng, 2016).

It became necessary to enhance the rail corridor between Nairobi and the port of Mombasa in order to make it effective and competitive due to the deterioration of the meter gauge railroad and the loss of significant cargo to road transport (Irandu, 2018). Chinese Premier Li Keqiang and Kenyan President Uhuru Kenyatta signed a US\$3.8 billion contract to build the 472 km SGR connecting the Port City of Mombasa with Nairobi, the Capital City of Kenya, during Li Keqiang's visit to Kenya in May 2014. The project called for the construction of a standard gauge railroad that would adhere to the highest modern standards and have a high capacity for both freight and passenger transportation. The Standard Gauge Railway has reduced the round trip from Mombasa to Nairobi to about eight hours for freight trains and about four hours for passengers, with average speeds between 80 and 120 km per hour (kph) for freight trains and 120 to 160 km per hour (kph) for passenger trains (Irandu & Owilla, 2020). Three main routes make up the Kenyan Standard Gauge Railway (SGR) Northern Corridor: Mombasa to Nairobi (Phase I), 120 km from Nairobi to Naivasha, and 369 km from Naivasha to Kisumu and Malaba. In Kenya's national development and spatial planning, the Lamu Port, South Sudan and Ethiopia Transport (LAPSSET) Corridor is probably going to be crucial. The Kenyan government claims that LAPSSET is the foundation for opening up and integrating Northern Kenya into the national economy (GoK, 2012: 6; Schindler et al., 2018; as per Irandu & Owilla, 2020). Kenya hopes to establish a "seamless" and "connected" Africa through the 2000 km long transportation corridor (LCDA, 2016). According to Kanai and Schindler (2019b; as indicated in Irandu & Owilla, 2020), the government plans to use LAPSSET to make northern Kenya a functional, globally connected, and nationally and internationally networked region.

President Xi Jinping traveled to Senegal, Rwanda, South Africa, and Mauritius in July 2018. More agreements that were partially related to the BRI were concluded as a result of his visit; 15 bilateral cooperation agreements with Rwanda and an agreement for future Belt and Road Cooperation with Senegal were signed, making Senegal the first country in western Africa to formally join the Initiative. It is a crucial Belt and Road extension because it is located in the westernmost portion of the African continent, according to Foreign Ministry spokesperson Geng Shuang (Foreign Ministry, 2018). China's bridgehead in western Africa is evolving into Senegal. The 8th Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) Ministerial Conference will take place in Senegal in 2021, it has already been decided (Beijing Declaration, 2018; mentioned in Kaczmarek, 2019). China achieved another victory in Africa when, on September 3,

2018, negotiations for a bilateral free trade agreement, which had been ongoing since December 2017, were concluded in the presence of Premier Li Keqiang and Prime Minister Pravind Jugnauth of Mauritius. The contract between China and an African partner will be the first of its kind when it is signed. China is the second-largest foreign investor and the country with the highest exports to Mauritius (after France). Due to its geographical location, Mauritius cannot be completely cut off from the BRI, but it does have a long history of positive relations and trade with India. Therefore, it would prefer not to officially participate in the BRI and not to take a clear stance in support of either China or India, which it vehemently opposes (Kaczmarek, 2019). A new railway line connecting Addis Ababa and Djibouti started operating commercially on January 1st, 2018. Its construction required a US\$ 3.3 billion loan from Chinese banks, making it the most expensive project China has ever undertaken in Africa. This railroad line might eventually be extended to South Sudan. Ethiopia's historical socialist path is sometimes blamed for the country's favorable view of the Chinese development model (Kiedy Afryka, 2018). Under the umbrella of "African socialism," several nations in Sub-Saharan Africa attempted to enact their own versions of socialism in the past. In contrast to the western model, which proved to be insufficiently effective in Sub-Saharan Africa, the Chinese model offers a development scenario that is both effective and an alternative.

1.3 The Case of Mali within BRI

Mali, a 21.5 million-population West African country, is a cultural center with ancient buildings and heritage. With a GDP of 19.6 billion US dollars in 2022, Mali's main exports include cotton, gold, and tobacco. The country's economy is dominated by agriculture and mineral resources. The Mali government is concentrating on the growth of mining, tourism, and agriculture while also encouraging the growth of the private sector and luring foreign investment. High-level meetings between China and Mali have been common since Mali's independence in 1960, and the two countries' relations have improved over time (National Development and Reform Commission of the People's Republic of China, 2015). The current President Keita has made four trips to China. China has given Mali a lot of assistance and helped Mali build a lot of economic and infrastructure projects, including water conservation projects, roads, railways, hospitals, and schools. China has also dispatched a team of aid workers to Mali to provide technical assistance and personnel training to Mali. China and Malaysia have also maintained a close working relationship in international affairs and have backed the just causes of Africa and developing nations together. In recent years, China-Malaysia relations have steadily improved their mutual assistance in the areas of security, culture, education, and other areas, making them one of the prime examples of amicable exchange between China and Africa (World Bank, 2019).

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) holds significant importance for Mali, a landlocked country in West Africa. Mali can benefit from the initiative in several ways. Firstly, it offers an opportunity for infrastructure development, particularly in the transportation and energy sectors, which can improve connectivity within Mali and enhance its trade links with neighboring countries and global markets. Secondly, the BRI can attract foreign investment and promote economic growth, providing avenues for job creation and poverty reduction. Additionally, the initiative can strengthen diplomatic ties between Mali and China, fostering cooperation and knowledge-sharing (The World Bank, 2019). The role of the Malian media in communicating the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) to the population is crucial in ensuring transparency, awareness, and understanding of the initiative's goals and benefits. The media serves as a bridge between the government, investors, and the public, providing accurate and comprehensive information about the BRI projects and their potential impact on Mali.

2. Malian Media; the Primary Factor Influencing Malian Awareness

Firstly, the media plays a vital role in disseminating information about the BRI's objectives, projects, and progress. Through news articles, reports, interviews, and documentaries, the media can educate the public about the infrastructure developments, investments, and economic opportunities brought by the BRI. This enables citizens to have a better understanding of how the initiative can potentially improve their lives and the country's overall development. The BRI has also fostered closer relations between China and Mali. By working together on infrastructure projects,

countries have been able to deepen their economic ties and increase mutual understanding. This has led to greater cooperation in other areas such as trade, investment, and cultural exchange. Additionally, the BRI has helped to bridge gaps in infrastructure development between developed and developing countries, creating a more level playing field for businesses and investors.

Secondly, the media can facilitate public debate and discussion around the BRI, allowing different perspectives and concerns to be heard. It can provide a platform for experts, policymakers, and citizens to voice their opinions, ask questions, and address potential challenges or risks associated with the initiative. This promotes transparency and accountability in the implementation of BRI projects. Furthermore, the BRI has the potential to create significant economic opportunities for Mali. By connecting markets and promoting trade, it can stimulate growth and development in regions that have traditionally been marginalized. This can lead to job creation, increased investment, and improved infrastructure, all of which can contribute to poverty reduction and increased standards of living. However, it is important to ensure that these benefits are shared equitably among all stakeholders, including local communities and small businesses. Additionally, environmental sustainability must be a key consideration in the planning and implementation of BRI projects. This includes minimizing negative impacts on ecosystems and promoting the use of renewable energy sources. Ultimately, the success of the BRI will depend on a collaborative approach that takes into account diverse perspectives and interests. By working together towards common goals, China and its partners can build a more interconnected world that benefits everyone involved.

Furthermore, the media can act as a watchdog, monitoring the progress of BRI projects, ensuring adherence to environmental and social standards, and reporting any potential issues or controversies. By holding both the government and investors accountable, the media helps ensure that the BRI benefits the population and contributes to sustainable development.

China and Mali have a long-standing relationship that has been strengthened over the years. Since Mali gained independence in 1960, the two countries have engaged in high-level exchanges, which have helped to develop bilateral relations. The Chinese government has been actively involved in the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which aims to promote economic growth and development across the world. However, it is important to ensure that both the government and investors are held accountable for their actions. This is where the media plays a crucial role in ensuring that the BRI benefits the population and contributes to sustainable development. By holding both parties accountable, the media helps to ensure that projects are implemented in a transparent and responsible manner. This not only benefits Mali but also strengthens China's relationship with other countries participating in the BRI. As such, it is important for both China and Mali to continue working together towards mutual development and prosperity.

3. Strategies for Improving Malian Citizens' Awareness of the 'Belt and Road' Initiative

Through the analysis of the cognition status and influencing factors of the construction of the "Belt and Road" of Mali citizens, it can be found that the citizens of Mali have some understanding of the connotation, goals, and factual approaches of the "Belt and Road" construction, but they lack completeness. Most of the interviewees are optimistic about the prospects of the "Belt and Road" construction and express their willingness to actively disseminate information about the "Belt and Road". At present, the mainstream media in Mali are paying more and more attention to the construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative. Most of the reports focus on the economic field. According to the report, to a certain extent, this has also affected some Mali citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction. This study puts forward five suggestions to enhance the international communication effect of the "Belt and Road" construction and enable Mali citizens to understand the "Belt and Road" construction more comprehensively and accurately.

3.1 Strengthening the Pertinence of Media Reports

As one of the least developed countries in Africa, Mali plays an important role in the construction of the "Belt and Road". However, according to the results of the previous analysis, the number of Mali media reports on the "Belt and Road" is

relatively small, and the reports are mainly concentrated on the economic aspects, and the number of reports on politics, society, and cultural exchanges is very small. Due to the lack of sufficient media reports and publicity, many Malian citizens have relatively low awareness of the construction of the "Belt and Road", which is not conducive to Mali's participation and development in the construction of the "Belt and Road". Therefore, strengthening the pertinence of media reports is an important strategy to enhance Malian citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction.

First, targeted reports should focus on issues of concern to Malian citizens. Media reports should dig deeper into the concerns and doubts of Mali citizens about the construction of the "Belt and Road", such as environmental protection issues and employment opportunities of construction projects. At the same time, the media should adopt local Mali language and cultural elements to better convey information.

Second, media reports should focus on publicizing the impact of the "Belt and Road" construction on Mali's economy and society. Reports should highlight the opportunities brought by the "Belt and Road" construction, such as infrastructure construction, investment and trade, as well as its positive impact on Mali's national development, such as promoting employment and improving living standards.

Third, media reports should emphasize the friendly relationship between China and Mali. China and Mali have a long-term friendly and cooperative relationship. Media reports should highlight this and strengthen understanding and exchanges between the two peoples. This will help to improve the trust and recognition of Mali citizens in the construction of the "Belt and Road".

Fourth, great attention should also be paid to the selection of reporting methods. Radio is the main medium of communication in Mali. There are hundreds of radio stations in Mali, operated by public, private and community operators. The BBC has a radio frequency in Bamako. China can set up a radio frequency in Mali, which can expand the communication effect of the "Belt and Road". Mali's TV audience is mainly concentrated in the capital, Bamako, where there is a public TV station, Office de la Radiodiffusion Television du Mali (ORTM), as well as some private TV stations. Chinese media can cooperate with Bamako's TV station to spread the "Belt and Road" initiative, and the target audience of these broadcasts is mainly the residents of Bamako. Mali's newspapers and Internet are also almost all published in Bamako, with low circulation. Bamako and Internet media are relatively developed, and there are many news portals, such as MaliWeb, Malijet, Bamako, Maliactu, etc. Chinese media can take advantage of these news portals. Strengthening the pertinence of media reports is an important strategy to enhance Malian citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction.

By focusing on the concerns of Malian citizens, emphasizing the impact of construction on Mali's economy and society, highlighting the friendly relations between China and Mali, and focusing on diversity and interaction, Malian citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction can be further improved, to promote Mali's participation and development in the "Belt and Road" construction.

3.2 Actively Responding to Mali Citizens' Demands

The previous survey results show that 63.59% of the respondents believe that the social environment will affect Mali citizens' perception of the "Belt and Road" construction. Therefore, in order for Mali citizens to fully understand the construction of the "Belt and Road", it is necessary to meet the demands of Mali citizens during the construction of the "Belt and Road", so as to create a good cognitive social environment. For example, among the "five links" of the "Belt and Road" construction, people-to-people bonds are one of the important items. To achieve people-to-people bonds, local citizens must feel the dividends brought about by the Belt and Road Initiative. In the process of developing business in Mali, Chinese enterprises must assume social responsibilities and strive for more social recognition. Malian citizens' awareness of the construction of the "Belt and Road" mainly comes from a large amount of investment, infrastructure improvement and job creation. However, Malian citizens also want more transparency in policies and information, so that ordinary citizens have a better understanding of this.

The investment and construction of Chinese enterprises in Mali should not only pay attention to the project itself, but also pay attention to social responsibility, to ensure that ordinary citizens in the project location can benefit from it and do a good job in environmental protection. In the investment and construction of Chinese enterprises in Mali, local employees should be used as much as possible to increase the job opportunities and income of local citizens and let them benefit first. Actively responding to citizens' demands and increasing the income of local citizens is the key to the smooth progress of the Belt and Road construction project in Mali. The Chinese government should take the lead in forming a consortium of enterprises to help Mali build roads, railways and other transportation infrastructure, so that Mali citizens can more widely join the beneficiary groups of the Belt and Road Initiative and improve their awareness of the Belt and Road Initiative. Through the joint construction of the "Belt and Road", China and Mali are closely related economically, and their interests are increasingly integrated. China should continue to strengthen policy interest linkages and cooperate with Mali to give preference to the areas of people's livelihood and poverty-stricken areas.

Mali is an agricultural country, and the agricultural population accounts for more than 80%. The Chinese side should continue to send agricultural experts to Mali to jointly build a China-Mali modernized agricultural industry cooperation and implement agricultural development projects, to lift more Malian farmers out of poverty. Ordinary citizens in Mali are most concerned about health care, transportation, and education. In terms of medical care, China will strengthen its medical assistance activities in Mali and help Mali achieve vaccine prevention and control of conventional diseases. In the field of transportation, we will focus on aiding and supporting infrastructure construction such as roads and bridges to further facilitate the travel of ordinary residents in Mali. China and Mali should also strengthen educational exchanges and cooperation so that more Chinese schools can run schools in Mali. It is also an effective way for the Chinese government and universities to provide scholarships for outstanding students from Mali to study in China. These measures will help enhance the understanding and friendship between the people of China and Malaysia and promote the smooth advancement of the "Belt and Road" construction.

3.3 Strengthening People-to-people and Cultural Exchanges

55.38% of the respondents believe that the international environment can affect their perception of the "Belt and Road" construction. Therefore, creating a good international environment is also an important way to improve Mali companies' awareness of the "Belt and Road". Among them, cross-cultural communication is an important way of international communication. With the continuous advancement of the "Belt and Road" initiative, more and more countries and regions have begun to join it, and Mali is one of them. However, compared with other countries, Mali citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction needs to be improved. Therefore, from the perspective of strengthening people-to-people and cultural exchanges, this article discusses how to improve Mali citizens' awareness of the construction of the "Belt and Road".

First of all, strengthen cultural exchanges. Culture is an important part of people's spiritual life and an important medium for exchanges between different countries and regions. Therefore, strengthening cultural exchanges is one of the important strategies to enhance Mali citizens' awareness of the construction of the "Belt and Road". Specifically, it can be achieved in the following ways: First, organize cultural activities. Chinese art groups and artists can be invited to Mali to hold cultural activities such as performances and exhibitions, so that Mali citizens can have a deeper understanding of Chinese culture, thereby enhancing their awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction. Second, they offer cultural courses. Chinese culture courses can be set up in schools, universities and other places in Mali so that Mali students can learn the Chinese language, history, culture and other aspects, to enhance their understanding of the "Belt and Road" construction. Secondly, strengthen educational exchanges. Education is an important way to cultivate talents and an important field of exchange between different countries. Therefore, strengthening educational exchanges is also one of the important strategies to improve Mali citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction. Specifically, it can be achieved in the following ways: First, establish educational cooperation projects.

It is possible to establish cooperative projects with Chinese universities and educational institutions, and jointly carry out cooperation in academic research and personnel training, so that Malian students and teachers can have a deeper understanding of China's education system and educational concepts, thereby enhancing the construction of the "Belt and Road" cognition. Second, carry out educational exchange activities. Students and teachers from Mali can be organized to exchange and study in China, allowing them to experience China's educational environment and education methods, to enhance their understanding of the "Belt and Road" construction. Finally, strengthen media exchanges. The media is an important channel for information dissemination and an important channel for exchanges between different countries. Therefore, strengthening media communication is also one of the important strategies to improve Mali citizens' awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction. Specifically, it can be achieved in the following ways: First, strengthen media cooperation. It is possible to establish a cooperative relationship with Chinese media organizations to jointly report on the progress of the "Belt and Road" construction so that Mali citizens can have a deeper understanding of the significance and impact of the "Belt and Road" construction. Second, carry out media exchange activities. It is possible to organize media professionals from Mali to go to China for exchange and study so that they can understand China's media development and media management system, to enhance their understanding of the "Belt and Road" construction.

Strengthening people-to-people and cultural exchanges is one of the important strategies to enhance the awareness of Mali citizens on the construction of the "Belt and Road". By strengthening cultural exchanges, educational exchanges and media exchanges, Mali citizens can have a deeper understanding of China and the construction of the "Belt and Road", thereby promoting friendly and cooperative relations between the two countries.

3.4 Strengthen the cooperation between Chinese and Mali media

From the study, 66.67% of the respondents believe that the media environment has a great influence on Mali citizens' cognition of the "Belt and Road" construction. Therefore, the Chinese media can actively provide news articles to the Mali media, and actively publicize and report to the public the content and achievements of cooperation with China under the background of the "Belt and Road" construction. For example, China is Mali's largest trading partner and as one of the source countries of investment, it has provided Mali with many high-quality industries and superior production capacity and supported Mali to achieve national rejuvenation and national prosperity. China has carried out construction projects such as the Guina Hydropower Station, solar energy demonstration villages, and agricultural technology demonstration centers in Mali, and has helped Mali solve the problems of drinking water, schooling, and medical treatment, and many other cooperation projects that benefit people's livelihood and benefit the people. For example, China has also actively supported Mali's fight against the COVID-19 epidemic and provided Mali with multiple batches of medical supplies and COVID-19 vaccines. Through the dissemination of this cooperation information, Mali citizens' understanding, and recognition of the "Belt and Road" will be enhanced, misunderstandings and prejudices will be eliminated, a good atmosphere of public opinion will be created, and friendly exchanges and cooperation between China and Mali will be promoted.

The Mali media can actively participate in and initiate various forms of exchange activities such as the "Belt and Road" media cooperation forum, media dialogues, and media training courses, and cooperate with Chinese media to spread the concept, goals, content, and achievements of the "Belt and Road" construction. Enhance mutual understanding and trust and build a consensus of co-construction and sharing. Mali media can also make full use of their own advantages and resources to carry out joint reporting, joint interviews, joint production and other forms of cooperation projects with Chinese media to jointly produce high-quality "Belt and Road" reports and improve communication effects and influence. Mali media can actively innovate and expand communication channels and platforms, cooperate with Chinese media in emerging fields such as the Internet, social media, and mobile terminals, and use multilingual, multi-media, and multi-dimensional methods to show Malian citizens the benefits of the "Belt and Road Initiative" Authentic looks and positive values.

3.5 Promoting the Active Participation of Multiple Subjects

With the continuous deepening of China's "Belt and Road" initiative, more and more countries and regions have begun to join this construction, and Mali is one of them. However, due to historical, cultural and economic reasons, Malian citizens have relatively low awareness and participation in the construction of the "Belt and Road". The survey results show that the channels for Mali citizens to form awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction include not only media channels, but also various interpersonal communication channels such as family, relatives and friends, classmates, teachers and students, and colleagues. Therefore, to improve Mali citizens' awareness of the construction of the "Belt and Road", it is necessary to promote the active participation of multiple subjects. The following is an analysis of how to achieve this from this perspective.

First, strengthen the government's publicity on the construction of the "Belt and Road". The government is the main force to promote the construction of the "Belt and Road". Strengthening the government's publicity on the construction of the "Belt and Road" will allow more Malian citizens to understand the significance and importance of this construction. The government can convey the information of the "Belt and Road" construction to the public through various forms of media publicity and organize various forms of publicity activities, so that the public can gradually realize the importance of the "Belt and Road" construction, thereby increasing public participation.

Second, strengthen the participation of social organizations. Social organizations are an important force to promote social progress. Strengthening the participation of social organizations in the construction of the "Belt and Road" will allow more Malian citizens to understand the importance and significance of this construction. Social organizations can pass on the information of the "Belt and Road" construction to the public through various forms of publicity activities and organize various forms of theme seminars, so that the public can gradually realize the importance of the "Belt and Road" construction, thereby improving public awareness. Participation.

Third, strengthen the participation of enterprises. Enterprises are an important force to promote economic development. Strengthening the participation of enterprises in the construction of the "Belt and Road" will allow more Malian citizens to understand the importance and significance of this construction. Enterprises can pass on the information about the "Belt and Road" construction to the public through various forms of publicity activities and organize various forms of theme seminars, so that the public can gradually realize the importance of the "Belt and Road" construction, thereby increasing public participation.

Finally, establish a mutual trust mechanism. Establishing a mutual trust mechanism can make all parties trust and support the construction of the "Belt and Road", thereby increasing public participation. The government can strengthen cooperation with other countries and regions in various ways, establish a mutual trust mechanism, and make other countries and regions trust and support the "Belt and Road" construction more, thereby attracting more Malian citizens to participate in the "Belt and Road" construction.

To improve Mali citizens' awareness and participation in the construction of the "Belt and Road", it is necessary to promote the active participation of multiple subjects. The government, social organizations and enterprises should work together to strengthen publicity, strengthen cooperation, establish a mutual trust mechanism, and let more Malian citizens understand the importance and significance of the "Belt and Road" construction, thereby increasing public participation and contributing to the "Belt and Road" construction.

4. The Way Forward

The article discusses the cognition status and influencing factors of the construction of the "Belt and Road" initiative among Mali citizens. It identifies that while citizens in Mali have some understanding of the initiative, their knowledge lacks completeness. However, most interviewees express optimism about the prospects of the "Belt and Road" construction and a willingness to disseminate information about it. The mainstream media in Mali has also started paying attention to the initiative, primarily focusing on the economic aspects. The article presents five suggestions to

enhance the international communication effect of the "Belt and Road" construction and improve the understanding of Mali citizens.

Firstly, the pertinence of media reports needs to be strengthened. This involves addressing the concerns and doubts of Mali citizens, highlighting the economic and societal impacts of the initiative, emphasizing the friendly relationship between China and Mali, and utilizing different media channels such as radio, television, newspapers, and the Internet to effectively convey information.

Secondly, it is essential to actively respond to the demands of Mali citizens. This includes meeting citizens' expectations during the construction process, ensuring transparency in policies and information, and promoting social responsibility among Chinese enterprises operating in Mali. By increasing the income and job opportunities for local citizens, construction projects can gain their support and improve awareness.

Thirdly, people-to-people and cultural exchanges should be strengthened. This can be achieved through cultural activities, offering cultural courses, educational exchanges, and media cooperation. By promoting understanding and friendship between the people of China and Mali, awareness of the "Belt and Road" construction can be enhanced.

Fourthly, cooperation between Chinese and Mali media needs to be strengthened. Chinese media can provide news articles and information about cooperation with Mali, highlighting the positive outcomes and benefits brought about by the "Belt and Road" construction. The Mali media, on the other hand, can participate in exchange activities, joint reporting, and joint production with Chinese media to produce high-quality reports and improve communication effects.

Lastly, active participation in multiple subjects should be promoted. This involves government publicity, participation of social organizations, engagement of educational institutions, and involvement of various interpersonal communication channels. By increasing the involvement and awareness of different stakeholders, the understanding and support for the "Belt and Road" construction can be broadened among Mali citizens.

In conclusion, the article emphasizes the importance of enhancing the awareness and understanding of the "Belt and Road" initiative among Mali citizens. By implementing the suggested strategies, such as strengthening media reports, responding to citizens' demands, promoting people-to-people and cultural exchanges, enhancing media cooperation, and encouraging active participation from various subjects, the construction of the "Belt and Road" in Mali can be better comprehended and supported. These efforts will contribute to the mutual benefits and cooperation between China and Mali, fostering a positive environment for the "Belt and Road" initiative in the country.

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